

Slime mold records from California

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Abstract: This note describes the slime molds (along with one member of the Acrasiomycetes) documented on a field trip to California during 2004.

Keywords: ecology, Myxomycetes, substrates

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During a lecture tour of northern California in November 2004 the opportunity was taken to collect myxomycetes in as wide a range of habitats as possible. The visit coincided with considerable mycological activity in the region and many of the sites proved to be rich in species.

Localities

California Coastal Chaparral Forest and Scrub Province – Central Coast Section

Alameda Co.

- 1: Berkeley – material collected from gardens and roadside trees
- 2: UC Berkeley Campus – parkland and relict forest

Contra Costa Co.

- 3: Tilden Regional Park – semi-natural woodland
- 4: Tilden Botanic Garden – parkland
- 5: Huckleberry Canyon – oak/laurel woodland

Santa Cruz Co.

- 6: Soquel – oak/pine woodland

San Mateo Co.

- 7: Ano Nueva Reserve – coastal pine scrub.

California Coastal Steppe-Mixed Forest-Redwood Forest Province – North Coast Section

Marin Co.

- 8: Muir Woods National Monument – redwood forest
- 9: Mont Tamalpais Park, Bon Tempe Reservoir area – mixed woodland

10: Point Reyes Reserve – Douglas fir/mixed woodland

Mendocino Co.

11: Albion – mixed woodland

12: Fern Canyon, Van Damme Memorial Park – Douglas fir forest

13: Jackson State Forest – redwood/Douglas fir forest

14: Jackson State Forest – pine/pygmy cypress forest

15: Navarro River valley – redwood/Douglas fir forest

Sonoma Co.

16: Kruse Rhododendron Reserve – mixed forest

17: Salt Point Park – coastal pine forest

18: Santa Rosa – street trees

19: Sebastopol – parkland

Species list

Notes: The letter “a” after the name of a species indicates a taxon more or less confined to the bark of living trees, whereas the letter “b” after a record indicates a specimen collected from a moist chamber culture prepared with tree bark, but not necessarily a species confined to bark of living trees in nature. The number refers to the site and the name in parentheses to the substrate for the record. Nomenclature follows Lado (2001-2021) with the exception of *Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa* varieties, *Lycogala terrestre* Fr. & Lindgr. and *Stemonitis nigrescens* Rex, for which such names were maintained.

Acrasiomycetes

- ◆ *Pocheina rosea* (Cienk.) Loeblich & Tappan (a). Recorded from locality 3 (*Sequoia*)

Ceratiomyxomycetes

- ◆ *Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa* (Muell.) T. Macbr. var. *fruticulosa*. Recorded from locality 3 (*Pseudotsuga*), 6 (*Pinus*), 8 (*Pseudotsuga*), 12 (*Pseudotsuga*), 13 (*Pseudotsuga*), 15 (*Pseudotsuga*), 16 (*Pinus*), 19 (*Pinus*)
- ◆ *Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa* (Muell.) T. Macbr. var. *arbuscula* (Berk. & Br.) Nann.-Bremek. Recorded from locality 9 (*Pinus*), 13 (*Pseudotsuga*)

Myxomycetes

Echinosteliales

- ◆ *Echinostelium apitectum* K.D. Whitney (a). Recorded from locality 2 (*Ginkgo*)
- ◆ *E. brooksii* K.D. Whitney (a). Recorded from locality 7 (*Pinus*)
- ◆ *E. colliculosum* K.D. Whitney & H.W. Keller (a). Recorded from locality 4 (*Lyonothamnus*), 12 (*Pinus*)
- ◆ *E. corynophorum* K.D. Whitney. Recorded from locality 1 (*Persea*)
- ◆ *E. fragile* Nann.-Bremek. (a). Recorded from locality 1 (*Cinnamomum*)
- ◆ *E. minutum* de Bary (a). Recorded from locality 1 (*Persea*, *Washingtonia*), 2 (*Melaleuca*, *Platanus*), 4 (*Lyonothamnus*), 18 (*Platanus*)

Cribariales

- ◆ *Cribraria argillacea* (Pers.) Pers. Recorded from locality 10 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *C. aurantiaca* Schrad. Recorded from locality 9 (*Pinus*), 10 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *C. cancellata* (Batsch) Nann.-Bremek. Recorded from locality 10 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *C. minutissima* Schwein. Recorded from locality 10 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *C. oregana* H.C. Gilbert. Recorded from locality 10 (*Pseudotsuga*), 13 (*Pseudotsuga*), 14 (*Pinus*), 17 (*Pinus*)
- ◆ *C. persoonii* Nann.-Bremek. Recorded from locality 10 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *C. piriformis* Schrad. Recorded from locality 10 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *Licaethalium olivaceum* (Ehrenb.) Rostaf. Recorded from locality 8 (*Pseudotsuga*)

Liceales

- ◆ *Licea kleistobolus* G.W. Martin (a). Recorded from locality 1 (*Cinnamomum*, *Persea*), 2 (*Platanus*), 3 (*Arbutus*), 4 (*Lyonothamnus*), 5 (*Umbellularia*), 7 (*Pinus*), 9 (*Quercus*), 18 (*Platanus*), 19 (*Malus*, *Quercus*)
- ◆ *L. marginata* Nann.-Bremek. (a). Recorded from locality 3 (*Salix*), 18 (*Platanus*)
- ◆ *L. microscopica* D.W. Mitchell (a). Recorded from locality 11 (*Sambucus mexicana*)
- ◆ *L. minima* Fr. (a). Recorded from locality 3 (*Eucalyptus*)
- ◆ *L. parasitica* (Zukal) G.W. Martin (a). Recorded from locality 1 (*Cinnamomum*), 3 (*Eucalyptus*, *Salix*), 9 (*Quercus*), 18 (*Platanus*), 19 (*Malus*, *Quercus*)
- ◆ *L. perexigua* T.E. Brooks & H.W. Keller (a). Recorded from locality 3 (*Arbutus*)
- ◆ *L. pusilla* Schrad. (a). Recorded from locality 14 (*Cupressus*)
- ◆ *L. pygmaea* (Meylan) Ing (a). Recorded from locality 7 (*Pinus*)
- ◆ *L. scyphoides* T.E. Brooks & H.W. Keller (a). Recorded from locality 2 (*Ginkgo*), 18 (*Platanus*)
- ◆ *L. testudinacea* Nann.-Bremek. (a). Recorded from locality 3 (*Arbutus*), 19 (*Malus*)

Reticulariales

- ◆ *Lycogala exiguum* Morgan. Recorded from locality 15 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *Lycogala terrestre* Fr. & Lindgr. Recorded from locality 2 (*Quercus*), 3,8 (*Pseudotsuga*), 9 (*Quercus*), 10, 16 (*Quercus*), 19 (*Quercus*)
- ◆ *Tubifera ferruginosa* (Batsch) J.F. Gmel. Recorded from locality 10 (*Pseudotsuga*)

Trichiales

- ◆ *Arcyria cinerea* (Bull.) Pers. Recorded from locality 3 (*Eucalyptus*) (b), 9 (*Alnus*), 10
- ◆ *A. denudata* (L.) Wettst. Recorded from locality 10 unknown
- ◆ *A. incarnata* (Pers.) Pers. Recorded from locality 8 (*Pseudotsuga*), 10, 13 (*Pseudotsuga*), 19 (*Quercus*)
- ◆ *A. obvelata* (Oeder) Onsberg. Recorded from locality 3 (*Eucalyptus*)
- ◆ *A. oerstedtii* Rostaf. Recorded from locality 12 (*Pseudotsuga*), 16 (*Pseudotsuga*), 17 (*Pinus*)
- ◆ *A. pomiformis* (Leers) Rostaf. Recorded from locality 1 (*Cinnamomum*, *Washingtonia*) (b), 17 (*Pinus*)
- ◆ *Calomyxa metallica* (Berk.) Niewland (a). Recorded from locality 1 (*Cinnamomum*)
- ◆ *Hemitrichia abietina* (Wigand) G. Lister. Recorded from locality 3 (*Eucalyptus*)

- ◆ *H. calyculata* (Speg.) M.L. Farr. Recorded from locality 10 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *Metatrichia floriformis* (Schwein.) Nann.-Bremek. Recorded from locality 6 (*Quercus*), 9 (*Quercus*), 12 (*Pseudotsuga*), 13 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *Perichaena chryosperma* (Currey) Lister (a). Recorded from locality 3 (*Eucalyptus*), 18 (*Platanus*), 19 (*Malus*, *Quercus*)
- ◆ *P. corticalis* (Batsch) Rostaf. Recorded from locality 3 (*Eucalyptus*)
- ◆ *P. depressa* Libert Recorded from locality 9 (*Lithocarpus*)
- ◆ *Trichia affinis* de Bary Recorded from locality 15 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *T. botrytis* (J.F. Gmel.) Pers. Recorded from locality 3 (*Eucalyptus*), 10 (*Pseudotsuga*), 15 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *T. decipiens* (Pers.) T. Macbr. Recorded from locality 10 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *T. favoginea* (Batsch Pers. Recorded from locality 9 (*Alnus*)
- ◆ *T. persimilis* P. Karst. Recorded from locality 10 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *T. scabra* Rostaf. Recorded from locality 2 (*Quercus*), 6 (*Quercus*), 9 (*Quercus*)
- ◆ *T. varia* (Pers.) Pers. Recorded from locality 3 (*Eucalyptus*), 9 (*Quercus*)
- ◆ *T. verrucosa* Berk. Recorded from locality 10 (*Pseudotsuga*)

Stemonidiales

- ◆ *Comatricha alta* Preuss. Recorded from locality 12 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *C. laxa* Rostaf. Recorded from locality 1 (*Cinnamomum*) (b)
- ◆ *C. nigra* (Pers.) J. Schröt. Recorded from locality 3 (*Quercus*)
- ◆ *Enerthenema papillatum* (Pers.) Rostaf. Recorded from locality 13 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *Macbrideola cornea* (G. Lister & Cran) Alexop. (a). Recorded from locality 19 (*Quercus*)
- ◆ *M. scintillans* H.C. Gilbert (a). Recorded from locality 1 (*Cinnamomum*, *Persea*), 2 (*Ginkgo*), 19 (*Malus*)
- ◆ *Paradiacheopsis cribrata* Nann.-Nremek. (a). Recorded from locality 1 (*Washingtonia*), 14 (*Cupressus*), 19 (*Malus*)
- ◆ *P. fimbriata* (G. Lister & Cran) Hertel (a). Recorded from locality 1 (*Cinnamomum*, *Washingtonia*), 14 (*Cupressus*)
- ◆ *P. solitaria* (Nann.-Bremek.) Nann.-Bremek. (a) Recorded from locality 3 (*Arbutus*)
- ◆ *Stemonitis axifera* (Bull.) T. Macbr. Recorded from locality 3 (*Quercus*)
- ◆ *S. flavogenita* E. Jahn. Recorded from locality 3 (*Eucalyptus*), 8 (*Pseudotsuga*), 9 (*Lithocarpus*)
- ◆ *S. fusca* Roth. Recorded from locality 3 (*Eucalyptus*), 8 (*Pseudotsuga*), 9 (*Quercus*), 15 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *S. nigrescens* Rex. (a). Recorded from locality 3 (*Eucalyptus*)
- ◆ *S. splendens* Rostaf. Recorded from locality 12 (*Pseudotsuga*), 15 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *Stemonitopsis hyperopta* (Meylan) Nann.-Bremek. Recorded from locality 13 (*Pseudotsuga*)
- ◆ *S. typhina* (F.H. Wiggers) Nann.-Bremek. Recorded from locality 3 (*Eucalyptus*), 8 (*Pseudotsuga*), 10, 17 (*Pinus*)
- ◆ *Symphytocarpus impexus* Ing & Nann.-Bremek. Recorded from locality 5 (*Umbellularia*)

Physarales

- ◆ *Badhamia affinis* Rostaf. (a) Recorded from locality 19 (*Quercus*)
- ◆ *Fuligo septica* (L.) F.H. Wiggers. Recorded from locality 15 (*Pseudotsuga*), 16 (*Quercus*)

- ◆ *P. album* (Bull.) Chevall. Recorded from locality 4 (*Populus*), 8 (*Pseudotsuga*), 9 (*Quercus*), 10, 14 (*Pinus*), 19 (*Quercus*)
- ◆ *Physarum bivalve* Fr. Recorded from locality 10 on leaf litter
- ◆ *P. cinereum* (Batsch) Pers. Recorded from locality
- ◆ *P. crateriforme* Petch. (a). Recorded from locality 3 (*Eucalyptus*)
- ◆ *P. globuliferum* (Bull.) Pers. Recorded from locality 16 (*Quercus*)
- ◆ *P. leucophaeum* Fr. Recorded from locality 2 (*Quercus*), 9 (*Alnus*), 10
- ◆ *P. pusillum* (Berk. & M.A. Curt.) G. Lister. Recorded from locality 1 (*Vinca*)
- ◆ *Didymium bahiense* Gottsberger. Recorded from locality 1 (*Hedera*), 2 (*Vinca*)
- ◆ *D. clavus* (Alb. & Schwein.) Rabenh. Recorded from locality on 10 on leaf litter
- ◆ *D. ilicinum* Ing. Recorded from locality 5 (*Umbellularia*), 19 on herbaceous litter. This species, a segregate from *D. squamulosum*, has been recognised as distinct for a century but was only described recently (Ing, 2020)
- ◆ *D. minus* (Lister) Morgan. Recorded from locality 5 (*Umbellularia*), 10 on herbaceous litter
- ◆ *D. squamulosum* (Alb. & Schwein.) Fr. Recorded from locality 1 (*Vinca*), 10 on leaf litter
- ◆ *D. sturgisii* Hagelst. (a). Recorded from locality 19 (*Malus*)

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